

SEARCH FOR NEW AMOEBACIDES. PART I

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β -(2-Alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamines have been synthesised through seven steps: Veratrole $\rightarrow$ 4-acylveratrole $\rightarrow$ 4-alkylveratrole $\rightarrow$ 2-alkyl-4:5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde $\rightarrow$ 2-alkyl-4:5-dimethoxycinamic acid $\rightarrow$ β -(alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionic acid $\rightarrow$ β -(2-alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionamide $\rightarrow$ β -(2-alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine.

The mode of action of emetine in amoebiasis has not been fully established. It is considered that emetine undergoes some degradation in the system, and on this basis Child and Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2010), Pyman (*Chem. & Ind.*, 1937, 58, 789), Goodwin *et al.* (*Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1948, 3, 44), Goodson *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1948, 3, 49, 62), Hall *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1842; 1952, 149) and Mahboob and Dhar (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 1) have synthesised several diaminines, which may be considered as cleavage products of the emetine molecule. None of them have proved to be superior to emetine *in vivo*.

If the opening of the emetine molecule (I) is considered along the dotted lines 'a', the molecule transforms to a compound of the type (II). It has been considered worthwhile to synthesise compounds of this type with various alkyl group substitution at R, to examine their amoebacidal activity.

Attempts to alkylate or acylate acylated 3:4-dimethoxyphenylethylamine by the Friedel-Crafts reaction proved abortive, although condensation was attempted in different solvents like ether, carbon disulphide and nitrobenzene, using anhydrous aluminium chloride as a condensing agent.

Synthesis of compounds of the type (II) has now been effected according to the following scheme:

Acetoveratrone was prepared in good yield by Pictet and Gams (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 2947) by condensing veratrole with acetyl chloride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The same method has been found to afford poor yields of acylveratroles (A) with higher acid chlorides. It has been found that if the above condensation is effected in presence of anhydrous zinc chloride at the boiling temperature of carbon disulphide, yields improve appreciably and the formation of tarry matter also decreases. Barger and Silverschmidt (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2924) reduced acetoveratrone (A: R'=Me) by the Clemmensen method in good yield. Following the same procedure, higher acylveratroles have been reduced to alkylveratroles (B) in 60 to 77% yield. Perkin and Weizman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 1648) prepared 2-methyl-4:5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde in 32% yield. Barger and Silverschmidt (*loc. cit.*) synthesised 2-ethyl-4:5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde, but no mention of yield was made. Both the aldehydes were prepared by the above workers according to Gattermann's aldehyde synthesis with the use of hydrogen cyanide. Aldehydes of the type (C) have now been prepared according to Adams' modified Gattermann synthesis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 1518) in 29 to 71% yields. Preparation of the compounds of the type (D) has been effected according to Knoevenagel's modified method of the Perkin reaction (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2598). This method is essentially the same as was applied by Robinson and Shinoda (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1977) for the preparation of 3:4-dimethoxycinnamic acid from veratraldehyde. Reduction of these cinnamic acids (D) by excess of sodium amalgam in the usual manner has yielded the corresponding dihydrocinnamic acids (E) in 75 to 88% yields. Haworth and Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1769) prepared β -3:4-dimethoxyphenylpropionamide in 30% yield by passing a stream of dry ammonia gas through the corresponding acid at 210° for two hours. By the same method β -2-alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl-propionamides (F) have been prepared in good yields. Conversion of the above amides (F) to β -(2-alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamines (II) has been effected in poor yields by the Hofmann reaction with the use of sodium hypochlorite. A mixture of bromine and caustic potash afforded poorer yield. Sodium hypochlorite yielded only a trace of (II, R=*n*-C₈H₁₇) from the amide (F: R'=*n*-C₈H₁₇) and in this case bromine and sodium methoxide in methanolic solution (Jeffreys, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1899, 22, 14) was successfully used.

* E X P E R I M E N T A L

α-Methyl-4:5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (C:R'=H).—To a mixture of homoveratrole (60 g.), zinc chloride (60 g.) and dry benzene (220 c.c.), taken in a three-necked flask fitted with a mercury seal stirrer and a reflux condenser, cooled in an ice bath, was passed dry HCl gas for 1 hour. Powdered AlCl₃ (anhyd., 75 g.) was then added and the passage of HCl was continued. After 3 hours, temperature was raised to 55° which was maintained for 2 hours. Stirring and the passage of HCl were continued all the time. The mass was then left overnight, decomposed by ice, and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 2 hours. Benzene layer was separated out and the aqueous layer was extracted twice with benzene. The combined benzene solution was washed with water, dried over calcium chloride and the residue after removal of benzene was distilled under vacuum, b.p. 120-22°/4 mm, yield 27 g. (40%). On crystallisation from dilute alcohol, it melted at 76°. The same aldehyde was prepared by Perkin and Weizman (*loc. cit.*) using hydrocyanic acid in 32% yield.

2-Methyl-4:5-dimethoxycinnamic Acid (D:R'=H).—A mixture of 2-methyl-4:5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (15 g.), malonic acid (15 g.), dry pyridine (30 c.c.) and piperidine (1 c.c.) was heated in anhydrous condition on a water-bath for 6 hours and then on a wire gauge for 1 hour. It was cooled and the contents were poured into a mixture of crushed ice and HCl (conc., 40 c.c.). The acid precipitated out as a yellowish solid. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 153°, yield 16.5 g. (89.2%). (Found: C, 64.6; H, 6.1; OMe, 27.4. C₁₂H₁₄O₄ requires C, 64.9; H, 6.3; OMe, 27.5%).

β-(2-Methyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionic Acid (E:R'=H).—2-Methyl-4:5-dimethoxycinnamic acid was dissolved in dilute caustic soda and was reduced with sodium amalgam (500 g. of 3.5%) in the usual manner. At the end of the reaction, the liquid was acidified with HCl, when an oil separated out. On cooling and stirring, the oil solidified. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 84-85°, yield 13 g. (86%). (Found: C, 64.8; H, 7.3. C₁₂H₁₆O₄ requires C, 64.3; H, 7.1%).

β-(2-Methyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionamide (F:R'=H).—Dry ammonia gas was passed through molten *β*-(2-methyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionic acid at 200° for 2 hours. The mass was then poured into water under stirring. The separated solid was filtered and washed with water. It crystallised in short colorless needles from hot water, m.p. 144-45°, yield 63%. (Found: N, 6.4. C₁₂H₁₇O₃N requires N, 6.3%).

β-(2-Methyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine (II:R=Me).—Finely powdered *β*-(2-methyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionamide (5 g.) was added to a solution of sodium hypochlorite (250 c.c. of 0.5 N) and stirred continually until the whole of amide dissolved completely (2 hours). The clear yellowish solution was then warmed on a water-bath for 2 hours, when a brown oil separated out. Solid KOH (30 g.) was added to

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected.

the solution and heating continued for another hour. It was then cooled and the amine extracted out with benzene. Benzene layer was dried over solid caustic potash, benzene was removed and the residual oil was distilled, b.p. 160-62°/6 mm, yield 0.9 g. (20%). The *picrate* crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 186°. The *hydrochloride* of the amine crystallised from ethyl acetate in colorless fine needles, m.p. 178°. (Found: C, 56.8; H, 7.7; N, 6.1. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2NCl$ requires C, 57.0; H, 7.8; N, 6.0%).

2-Ethyl-4:5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (C: R' = Me).—A mixture of ethylveratrole (Barger and Silverschmidt, *loc. cit.*) (127 g.), zinc cyanide (127 g.) and dry benzene (400 c.c.) was subjected to Gattermann's aldehyde synthesis, modified by Adams according to a procedure described under compound (C: R' = H). The aldehyde distilled at 155-60°/9 mm, yield 65 g. (44%). The aldehyde was prepared by Barger and Silverschmidt using hydrogen cyanide.

2-Ethyl-4:5-dimethoxycinnamic acid (D: R' = Me) crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless lustrous needles, m.p. 164-65°, yield 82%. (Found: C, 66.2; H, 6.7; OMe, 26.4. $C_{13}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 66.1; H, 6.8; OMe, 26.2%).

β -(2-Ethyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionic acid (E: R' = Me) was prepared by reducing 2-ethyl-4:5-dimethoxycinnamic acid with excess of sodium amalgam in the usual manner (yield 75%). It crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless short needles, m.p. 55-56°. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 7.4. $C_{13}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 65.5; H, 7.6%).

β -(2-Ethyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionamide (F: R' = Me) crystallised in colorless short prismatic needles from hot water, m.p. 162°, yield 65%. (Found: N, 6.0. $C_{13}H_{18}O_3N$ requires N, 5.9%).

β -(2-Ethyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine (II: R = Et).— *β -(2-Ethyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionamide* (20 g.) was treated with sodium hypochlorite solution (400 c.c. of 0.5 N) in the usual manner, as described under compound (II: R = Me). The amine boiled at 160-62°/3 mm, yield 4 g. (23%). *Picrate* crystallised from alcohol in light brown needles, m.p. 190-91°. Its *hydrochloride* crystallised from ethyl acetate in colorless needles, m.p. 193-94°. (Found: C, 58.3; H, 8.2; N, 5.9. $C_{12}H_{20}O_2NCl$ requires C, 58.7; H, 8.1; N, 5.7%).

3:4-Dimethoxyphenylethyl Ketone (A: R' = Et): *Method I*.—To a solution of veratrole (75 g.) and propionyl chloride (50 g.) in dry CS_2 (300 c.c.) was added $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 50 g.) portion-wise at ice-cold temperature. After the addition was over, the flask was maintained at this temperature for 6 hours and later on it was warmed on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The contents were then poured on ice. CS_2 layer was separated out and the aqueous layer was extracted twice with fresh CS_2 . From the combined carbon disulphide solution, the solvent was removed and the residue was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with dilute NaOH solution and water successively; ether was removed and the residual oil was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 157-60°/5 mm, yield 33 g. (31%).

Method II.—A mixture of veratrole (120 g.), propionyl chloride (100 g.), CS_2 (400 c.c.) and powdered $ZnCl_2$ (anhyd., 100 g.) was gently refluxed on a water-bath

for 4 hours, when HCl fumes continually evolved. CS₂ was distilled off, the residual mass was decomposed by boiling with water for 1 hour and the oily liquid was extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed with dilute NaOH and water successively, dried over anhydrous calcium chloride, and the residual oil after removal of ether gave on distillation the ketone (60 g., 35.7% yield); b.p. 157-59°/4 mm.

The ketone solidified on cooling and on crystallisation from alcohol yielded colorless short prisms, m.p. 58°. (Found: C, 67.9; H, 7.3. C₁₁H₁₄O₂ requires C, 68.0; H, 7.2%). The *semicarbazone* crystallised in colorless needles from alcohol, m.p. 193°. (Found: N, 16.8. C₁₂H₁₇O₃N₃ requires N, 16.7%).

1-n-Propyl-3:4-dimethoxybenzene (B:R' = Et).—Granulated zinc (400 g.) was amalgamated with 5% mercuric chloride solution (800 c.c.) for 1 hour. This zinc was washed with water, covered with 10% HCl and allowed to boil. To the boiling solution 3:4-dimethoxyphenylethyl ketone (85 g.) was added during the course of an hour. Boiling was continued for further 6 hours and a total amount of 250 c.c. of HCl (conc.) was added at regular intervals. It was then cooled and extracted with ether. The ether solution was dried, the ether removed and the residual oil distilled in vacuum, b.p. 112-14°/4 mm, yield 52 g. (66.6%). (Found: C, 73.1; H, 9.2; OMe, 33.9. C₁₁H₁₆O₂ requires C, 73.3; H, 8.9; OMe, 34.4%).

2-n-Propyl-4:5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (C:R' = Et).—Dry HCl gas was passed through a mixture of 1-n-propyl-3:4-dimethoxybenzene (67 g.), zinc cyanide (50 g.) and dry benzene (250 c.c.). The mixture was stirred mechanically and after one hour AlCl₃ (anhyd., 40 g.) was added. Subsequent operations were the same as described under compound (C:R' = Me). It boiled at 158-60°/4 mm, yield 20 g. (29%). Its *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from alcohol in red needles, m.p. 185°. The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol in colorless fine needles, m.p. 187°. (Found: N, 16.0. C₁₃H₁₉O₃N₄ requires N, 15.8%).

2-n-Propyl-4:5-dimethoxycinnamic acid (D:R' = Et) crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless short needles, m.p. 155°, yield 83.3%. (Found: C, 67.6; H, 7.4; OMe, 24.6. C₁₄H₁₈O₄ requires C, 67.2; H, 7.2; OMe, 24.8%).

β-(2-n-Propyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionic acid (E:R' = Et) crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 68°, yield 88%. (Found: C, 67.1; H, 7.8. C₁₄H₂₀O₄ requires C, 66.7; H, 7.9%).

β-(2-n-Propyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionamide (F:R' = Et) crystallised from hot water in colorless short prisms, m.p. 110°, yield 85%. (Found: N, 5.7. C₁₄H₂₁O₃N requires N, 5.57%).

β-(2-n-Propyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine (II:R = n-Pr).—*β-(2-n-Propyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionamide* (10 g.) was treated with sodium hypochlorite solution (200 c.c. of 0.5 N) in the usual manner, described previously. The amine distilled at 160-62°/4 mm, yield 4.5 g. (51%). Its *picrate* crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 177° (decomp.).

The *amine hydrochloride* crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and absolute alcohol in fine colorless needles, m.p. 235-37°. (Found: C, 57.3; H, 8.5; N, 5.7. $C_{13}H_{22}O_2NCl$ requires C, 57.9; H, 8.2; N, 5.2%)

3:4-Dimethoxyphenyl-n-propyl Ketone (A:R' = *n*-Pr): *Method I*.—Veratrole (100 g.) and *n*-butyryl chloride (80 g.) in CS_2 (400 c.c.) were allowed to condense in presence of $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 60 g.) at ice-cold temperature in a manner described in the case of compound (A:R' = Et; method I). The ketone distilled at 160-65°/4 mm, yield 21 g. (14%).

Method II.—Veratrole (80 g.) and *n*-butyryl chloride (75 g.) in CS_2 (400 c.c.) were allowed to react in presence of $ZnCl_2$ (anhyd., 75 g.) according to the procedure described under compound (A:R' = Et; method II). It yielded 40 g. of the ketone (36.6%). The ketone crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 54°. (Found: C, 69.4; H, 7.2. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 69.2; H, 7.7%). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine colorless needles, m.p. 135°. (Found: N, 15.9; OMe, 23.4. $C_{13}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires N, 15.8; OMe, 23.4%).

1-n-Butyl-3:4-dimethoxybenzene (B:R' = *n*-Pr).—*3:4-Dimethoxyphenyl-n-propyl ketone* was reduced by the Clemmensen reduction as described before. It boiled at 112-15°/4 mm, yield 69%. (Found: C, 73.9; H, 9.9. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 74.2; H, 9.5%).

2-n-Butyl-4:5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (C:R' = *n*-Pr).—To a mixture of *1-n-butyl-3:4-dimethoxybenzene* (60 g.), zinc cyanide (75 g.), dry benzene (250 c.c.), cooled in an ice bath, was passed dry HCl. After one hour powdered $AlCl_3$ (anhyd., 40 g.) was added and the subsequent operations were conducted in a manner described before. The aldehyde distilled at 195-97°/6 mm, yield 48 g. (71%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from alcohol in brick-red needles, m.p. 206°.

The *semicarbazone* crystallised in fine colorless needles from alcohol, m.p. 144°. (Found: N, 15.2; OMe, 22.1. $C_{14}H_{21}O_3N_2$ requires N, 15.0; OMe 22.2%).

2-n-Butyl-4:5-dimethoxycinnamic acid (D:R' = *n*-Pr) crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 114°, yield 95%. (Found: C, 68.4; H, 7.4. $C_{15}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 68.2; H, 7.6%).

β-(2-n-Butyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionic Acid (E:R' = *n*-Pr).—*2-n-Butyl-4:5-dimethoxycinnamic acid* was reduced with sodium amalgam in the usual manner. The acid crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colorless needles, m.p. 58-59°, yield 89%. (Found: C, 67.4; H, 8.5. $C_{15}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 67.7; H, 8.3%).

β-(2-n-Butyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionamide (F:R' = *n*-Pr) crystallised from hot water in colorless short prisms, m.p. 105°, yield 75%. (Found: N, 5.4; OMe, 23.5. $C_{16}H_{23}O_3N$ requires N, 5.6; OMe, 23.4%).

β -(2-*n*-Butyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine (II:R = *n*-Bu).—The above propionamide (F:R' = *n*-Pr) (12 g.) was treated with sodium hypochlorite solution (300 c.c. of 0.5 N) in the usual manner, as described before. The amine distilled at 195°/10 mm, yield 2 g. (28%).

The *picrate* crystallised from alcohol in light brown needles, m.p. 152-53°. The *hydrochloride* was crystallised from absolute alcohol in colorless fine needles, m.p. 157°. (Found: C, 61.1; H, 9.1; N, 5.3. C₁₄H₂₄O₂NCl requires C, 61.4; H, 8.8; N, 5.1%).

3:4-Dimethoxyphenyl-*n*-amyl Ketone (A:R' = *n*-C₅H₁₁).—Veratrole (15 g.), *n*-caproyl chloride (15 g.), CS₂ (100 c.c.) and ZnCl₂ (anhyd., 15 g.) were worked up in the usual manner. It distilled at 150°/1 mm, yield 12 g. (49%). The ketone was a viscous liquid and did not solidify. Its *semicarbazone* was crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 178°. (Found: N, 14.6. C₁₅H₂₃O₂N₂ requires N, 14.4%).

1-*n*-Hexyl-3:4-dimethoxybenzene (B:R' = *n*-C₅H₁₁).—3:4-Dimethoxyphenyl-*n*-amyl ketone was reduced by the Clemmensen reduction method in the usual manner. It boiled at 134-36°/2 mm, yield 77%. (Found: C, 75.8; H, 10.2. C₁₄H₂₂O₂ requires C, 76.7; H, 9.9%).

2-*n*-Hexyl-4:5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (C:R' = *n*-C₅H₁₁).—The aldehyde prepared in the usual manner distilled at 168-70°/2 mm, yield 30%. It did not solidify even on cooling. Its 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from alcohol in brick-red fine needles, m.p. 210°. Its *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 134-35°. (Found: N, 13.8. C₁₆H₂₂O₂N₂ requires N, 13.5%).

2-*n*-Hexyl-4:5-dimethoxycinnamic acid (D:R' = *n*-C₅H₁₁) crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless short needles, m.p. 95-96°, yield 77%. (Found: C, 70.1; H, 8.3. C₁₇H₂₇O₄ requires C, 69.8; H, 8.2%).

β -(2-*n*-Hexyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionic Acid (E:R' = *n*-C₅H₁₁).—2-*n*-Hexyl-4:5-dimethoxycinnamic acid was reduced by sodium amalgam in the usual manner. It crystallised in colorless microneedles from dilute alcohol, m.p. 70-72°, yield 94%. (Found: C, 69.1; H, 9.1. C₁₇H₂₆O₄ requires C, 69.4; H, 8.8%).

β -(2-*n*-Hexyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionamide (F:R' = *n*-C₅H₁₁).—The amide on twice crystallisation from dilute alcohol appeared in colorless short needles m.p. 58-60°, yield 60%. (Found: N, 4.6. C₁₇H₂₇O₂N requires N, 4.8%).

β -(2-*n*-Hexyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine (II:R = *n*-C₅H₁₁).— β -(2-*n*-Hexyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-propionamide (5 g.) was dissolved in dry methanol (10 c.c.). This was added to a solution of sodium methoxide prepared out of sodium (0.8 g.) and methanol (30 c.c.). To the cold solution bromine (2.6 g.) was added and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The solution was made just acidic with acetic acid and methanol was removed by distillation. The residual mass was then hydrolysed with NaOH solution (25%). It was then extracted with benzene and the benzene solution was twice extracted with (dilute) HCl. The combined acid

solution was made alkaline with NaOH solution and the separated amine was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was dried over solid caustic potash, and on addition of a saturated solution of dry hydrogen chloride in ether, to the ethereal solution of the amine, hydrochloride of the amine separated out, yield 1.5 g. (30%). It crystallised from absolute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 123-24°. (Found: C, 63.8; H, 9.4; N, 4.7. $C_{16}H_{26}O_2NCl$ requires C, 63.7; H, 9.3; N, 4.6%). Its *picrate* crystallised from dilute alcohol in light brown needles, m.p. 162-63°.

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